

Base4NFDI Integration Workshop:

Synthesis Document – March 2025

Introduction

On **5 March 2025** a Base4NFDI initiated workshop was held with representatives of the NFDI consortia. The 2-hour virtual workshop was attended by over 80 people from NFDI (coordinators, speakers, technical personnel and service teams). The Base4NFDI services are currently in the situation where some are in or moving to Integration Phase. This is the critical phase where take-up and adoption of the services should be part of consortia activities. However, it should be clear how and where the consortia can interact and engage with a service. Many are also planning the second round of their consortia projects. As pointed out in a recent DFG report by the NFDI expert committee¹, cross-consortia services are a key element in the development of the NFDI and their development should be participatory. As the consortia develop further, inclusion of commitment to the Base4NFDI services is essential to the sustainability of NFDI, which was also the topic of a [previous integration workshop](#) in 2024.

The aims of the workshop were:

- To showcase and discuss practical approaches to work with Base4NFDI to start the integration process
- To present examples of incubators and similar opportunities for consortia engagement
- To discuss how Base processes can be adopted in prolongation proposals
- To put forward and identify communication channels between the consortia, Base4NFDI (service stewards) and the basic service teams

¹ Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft. (2024). Zukunft der NFDI nach Auslaufen der Bund-Länder-Vereinbarung im Jahr 2028. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13961033>

The workshop agenda included a brief introduction and presentation from Base4NFDI, a review of the current state of integration efforts, and a session on incorporating Base activities into future consortia proposals. Participants then joined breakout groups based on their stakeholder roles, followed by a shared feedback session. Base4NFDI placed strong emphasis on capturing key insights and documenting outcomes for future reference. The workshop proceeded as planned, with a smooth flow and active participation throughout.

Identified Take-Aways:

KEY TAKE AWAY 1

Service Roadshows and presentations provided by Base4NFDI are a helpful instrument to get a first overview of the services.

- Clarification of the **benefits** and **functionality** of a service is needed. This will reduce the challenge of competing services in consortia and transition to Base4NFDI services, as well as a reluctance to adopt a still developing service.

KEY TAKE AWAY 2

Communicating directly with **NFDI-member institutions** should be part of the engagement process.

- In most cases this is the role of the consortia to make these links, however Base4NFDI needs to consider direct approaches with institutions and decide on an effective strategy and how effort that goes into communication with consortia can be redistributed for institutional engagement.
- Including partner institutions directly in basic service proposals was named as a success factor.

KEY TAKE AWAY 3

Arrange more targeted contacts between service teams and the consortia.

- Overview presentations are good to start with or to generate interest. However, for real integration, experts from the basic services and experts from the relevant community services need to talk to each other, such as 'Drop-in clinics' or 'deep-dive' sessions.

KEY TAKE AWAY 4

Align the Base4NFDI service Incubators process.

- Incubators, focus groups and test-beds are a success factor but the process should be standardised and made clear for all who wish to be involved. Ideally all such involvement could be called 'Incubators' and have a standardized on-boarding process, clear terms of action, time needed (e.g. Way of Working template) and similar processes.

KEY TAKE AWAY 5

Support NFDI consortia proposal submission for their next rounds.

- The consortia find it helpful if Base4NFDI prepares text to include across their consortia proposal text, highlighting how they intend to work with the Base4NFDI services and aligning with relevant Task Areas.

Key Actions for Base4NFDI

KEY ACTION 1

Base4NFDI should focus efforts on providing more high-level, easily understandable information about basic services such as fact sheets.

- **Action:** Create service fact sheets. Wished-for information is summarised as follows:
 - Target-groups of each service, responsibilities of consortium/basic service (e.g. via SLAs),
 - Technical interoperability requirements (what needs to be interoperable? E.g. API, metadata standard, ...),
 - Current and projected TRL of the service
- **Action:** Continue to provide the roadshows, Base4NFDI newsletters and regular information about the services to the consortia.

KEY ACTION 2

Provide more detailed information and business case about why the Base service should be adopted over and above a competing service.

- Some clear high level overview should be presented. Concrete use cases would work here. Information on quality assurance and sustainability from Base4NFDI's side (how is it taken care of in our phases/process).
- **Action:** Create a use cases page on the Base4NFDI website. The target group is consortia or institutional infrastructure leadership.

KEY ACTION 3

Support the consortia as much as possible in shaping the development of basic services.

- Help to support in consolidating the needs and opinions about a basic service for their community.
 - **Action:** Create a 'Steps to Integration Roadmap Guidance' document. Create a table template that lists the service and criteria for their usefulness.
- Be clear in terms of what is actually expected from a consortium to integrate a service.
 - **Action:** Provide a template for a roadmap for onboarding Base4NFDI services in consortia.

- **Action:** Prepare a blueprint for our presence at consortia meetings, a 'kit' that the service stewards/Base4NFDI staff can follow before-during-after a consortia event.
 - This can include: analysing the services surveys, an example agenda for a roundtable or discussion topics, presentation materials

KEY ACTION 4

Create a standardised process for services to adapt an incubator process.

- **Action:** Establish a format with the services about the incubators and update the service websites with this information.
Information should include:
 - Who the incubators are targeted at
 - Timeframe and technical expertise needed
 - Publish clear information about the service incubators on the respective landing page and a central incubator page.
 - Dates and rounds
 - Regularly advertised in the Base4NFDI newsletter and rocketchat and on the website
 - In the case that certain services do not have an incubator program it should be mentioned why on the web page of the service.

KEY ACTION 5

Prepare comprehensive text for the next round proposals using the DFG NFDI 2025 template which highlights:

- **Action:** Write an example text that aligns with the DFG question: How does your consortium plan to integrate Base4NFDI services? Underline the need for resources/person months for consortia to tackle Base4NFDI integration. Consortia are lacking personnel (in general and with the right expertise) to support basic services, integrate them and communicate about them into their community and partner institutions.
- Try to align Base4NFDI activities with planned TAs, for example: TAs that might address:
 - Interoperability
 - Consortia Service catalogue
 - OneNFDI

Integration Workshop

Key Actions

Base4NFDI should focus efforts on providing more high-level, easily understandable information about basic services such as fact sheets.

	<i>Responsible</i>	<i>When (2025)</i>
Create service fact sheets	Base4NFDI, Service Teams	Q2-3
Continue to provide Service Roadshows	SERs, Service Teams	Ongoing

Provide more detailed information and business case about why the Base service should be adopted over and above a competing service.

	<i>Responsible</i>	<i>When</i>
Create a use cases page on the Base4NFDI website. The target group is consortia or institutional infrastructure leadership.	Base4NFDI (TF Website)	Q3

Support the consortia as much as possible in shaping the development of basic services.

	<i>Responsible</i>	<i>When</i>
Create a 'Steps to Integration Roadmap Guidance' document. Create a table template which lists the service and criteria for their usefulness.	Base4NFDI, SERs	Q2
Provide a template for a roadmap for onboarding Base4NFDI services in consortia.	SERs, Base4NFDI (together with consortia)	Q2
Prepare a blueprint for our presence at consortia meetings, a 'kit' that the service stewards/Base4NFDI staff can follow before-during-after a consortia event.	SERs	Q3

Create a standardised process for services to adapt an incubator process.

	<i>Responsible</i>	<i>When</i>
Establish a format with the services about the incubators and update the service websites with this information.	SERs, TA4, Service Teams	Q3

Prepare comprehensive text for the next round proposals using the DFG NFDI 2025 template.

	<i>Responsible</i>	<i>When</i>
Write an example text that aligns with the DFG question: How does your consortium plan to integrate Base4NFDI services? Underline the need for resources/person months for consortia to tackle Base4NFDI integration. Consortia are lacking personnel (in general and with the right expertise) to support basic services, integrate them and communicate about them into their community and partner institutions.	TA4 together with consortia	Q1